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Effects of Humic Acid and Gibberellic Acid Applications on Germination and Early Seedling Development in Lentil (*Lens culinaris* Medik.)

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Abstract: Seed germination and early seedling development are critical indicators for plant density, thereby higher yield in lentil, particularly in semi-arid regions. The experiment was carried out to evaluate how priming treatments with humic acid (HA) and gibberellic acid (GA₃) influence seed germination behavior and the early stages of seedling development under controlled conditions. The experiment included two concentrations of HA and GA₃ over control. Significant differences were observed among treatments for germination percentage, mean germination time, germination index, germination uniformity, germination energy and root length (p<0.01). The GA₂ (100 mg L⁻¹ GA₃), treatment produced the highest germination percentage (97.5%) and shortest germination time (1.037 days). Although GA₂ improved germination percentage and root elongation, the shortest mean germination time was observed in the control treatment. The shortest germination time (1.037 days) was determined in control. GA treatments also promoted root elongation (up to 6.30 cm) that indicates enhanced early radicle development. In contrast, the higher HA resulted in the lowest germination percentage (75.0%) and reduced germination uniformity, suggesting an inhibitory effect at elevated concentrations. There were no statistically significant differences among the treatments in terms of biomass parameters. In addition, gibberellic acid applications did not increase seedling vigor index values. Overall, gibberellic acid improved several germination-related traits, particularly germination percentage and root elongation, whereas humic acid required careful dosage adjustment to avoid negative effects on early growth.

Keywords

Germination

Legumes

giberellic acid

humic acid

lens culinaris

seed priming

1. Introduction

Archaeological evidence supported by radiocarbon dating techniques indicates that lentil (*Lens culinaris* M.) is one of the earliest domesticated pulse crops (Sonnante et al., 2009). Owing to its rich chemical composition, lentil serves as a major source of dietary protein in particularly developing and underdeveloped regions, thus, it plays a crucial role in food security and human nutrition. Lentil is cultivated on approximately 6.4 million hectares with an annual production of nearly 7.9 million tons on the world, whereas it occupies about 242 thousand hectares with an output of 405 thousand tons in the Türkiye. Red lentil is predominantly grown in the Southeastern Anatolia region, contributing significantly to both regional and national economies. Moreover, Siirt is one of the leading lentil-producing provinces that covers 14.714 hectares with a production of 30.464 tons and an average yield of 2.070 kg ha⁻¹ (FAO, 2024; TÜİK, 2024).

Rapid population growth and widening income disparities have contributed to a decline in the availability and affordability of animal-based foods. Consequently, dependency on plant-based agricultural products has increased (Rampal, 2018). Lentil is valued not only for its high protein content and mineral composition but also for its importance in crop rotation systems. Through symbiotic associations with *Rhizobium* species forming root nodules, the plant fixes atmospheric nitrogen and enriches soil fertility, thereby benefiting subsequent crops (Ünver et al., 1999). Given its nutritional value and nitrogen-fixing capacity, lentil is considered a key crop in both human and animal nutrition as well as sustainable farming systems. Nevertheless, lentil production is constrained by numerous biotic and abiotic stress factors, including drought, soil salinity, extreme heat or cold, heavy-metal buildup resulting from industrial processes, nutrient imbalances, and pressure from diseases and insect pests. These factors collectively result in significant yield and quality losses (Sehgal et al., 2017; Delahunty et al., 2018; Erman et al., 2022; Çiğ et al., 2024). Germination and early seedling development are among the most critical stages influencing lentil yield. Achieving high productivity depends on selecting regionally adapted and high-yielding cultivars but also on optimizing agronomic practices that promote both above- and below-ground growth and enhance resistance to diseases (El haddad et al., 2023; Noor et al., 2024). Plant growth and development are mainly regulated by endogenous factors, particularly plant hormones. These growth-regulating compounds may be synthesized within the plant or applied externally, and they can influence a wide range of physiological processes even at very low concentrations. A molecule is considered a plant hormone if it is naturally produced within the plant, can be transported to other organs, and regulates developmental processes at the destination site (Sultana et al., 2025). Plant growth regulators (PGRs) are generally classified into growth-promoting groups (auxins, cytokinins, gibberellins etc.) and growth-inhibiting ones (abscisic acid, ethylene etc.) play a regulatory role particularly in fruit ripening (Taiz and Zeiger, 2010). Numerous studies have shown that essential nutrients interact with PGRs and boost plant growth responses (Ahmad et al., 2023).

Humus, the primary component of soil organic matter, is formed through the long-term decomposition of plant residues and plays a pivotal role in maintaining soil fertility (Aydın and Kılıç, 2011). Increasing reliance on chemical fertilizers has reduced humus levels in many soils, however, humic substances facilitate nutrient uptake by improving soil structure and chemical properties. Humic acid, which constitute a major fraction of humus, enhance the uptake of nutrients, vitamins, and trace elements (Nardi et al., 2002). Among materials used to enrich soil organic matter content, humic acid has gained significant attention due to its effectiveness in improving soil fertility and crop productivity. Studies evaluating humic acid showed positive effects on nutrient availability and plant performance (Nardi et al., 2002). On the other hand, gibberellic acid (GA) is a well-known phytohormone involved in breaking seed dormancy and regulating germination and early growth (Finch-Savage and Leubner-Metzger, 2006). Plant growth regulators such as humic acids and gibberellic acid can influence plant

growth directly or indirectly by improving soil physical and chemical properties, increasing cation exchange capacity, and stabilizing pH. These regulators also play essential roles under stress conditions, supporting plant growth and strengthening tolerance mechanisms against adverse environmental factors (Nardi et al., 2002; Yamaguchi, 2008).

The hypothesis of this study is that seed priming treatments with HA and GA will enhance germination and early seedling development. Accordingly, the objective of the experiment is to investigate the effects of different concentrations of HA and GA on the germination characteristics and early seedling growth parameters of lentil plants.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Materials

Tigris lentil cultivar, developed through selection breeding at the GAP International Agricultural Research and Training Center, was used in the experiment. Seeds were collected from the same production year and storage conditions to ensure homogeneity. GA₃ (≥90% purity, Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) was dissolved in a small volume of ethanol and then diluted with distilled water to obtain 50 and 100 mg L⁻¹ solutions. Humic acid (commercial formulation, containing 12% humic acid and 3% fulvic acid, pH 9.5; Tima Agriculture, Türkiye) was diluted with distilled water to obtain 2000 and 4000 mg L⁻¹ solutions. GA is known for its role in regulating plant growth, breaking seed dormancy, and stimulating germination (Taiz and Zeiger, 2010). HA is an organic compound that improves plant physiological functions, enhances nutrient uptake, and increases tolerance to salinity (Tiryaki and Korkmaz, 2005).

2.1.1. Experimental conditions

The study was carried out in the Field Crops Laboratory of Siirt University, Siirt, Türkiye. The experiment was conducted in an incubator located in the Field Crops Laboratory. During the experiment, the incubator temperature was maintained at a constant 25 °C, and a dark environment was ensured throughout the experimental period.

2.2. Methods

Seeds were sterilized by 5% sodium hypochlorite for 10 minutes and then rinsed several times with distilled water to remove to avoid residue. Seeds were air-dried on the filter papers. Distilled water, GA and HA solutions were used for seed priming. Five seed priming agents (Control: Distilled water, GA1: 50 mg L⁻¹ GA₃, GA2: 100 mg L⁻¹ GA₃, HA1: 2000 mg L⁻¹ HA, HA2: 4000 mg L⁻¹ HA) were used in the experiment. The selected GA and HA concentrations were based on previous studies reporting improved germination and early seedling growth under similar ranges (Gulser et al, 2010; Gürbüz et al, 1996). A 15 ml of priming solutions were added into each petri including related seeds (Asgharipour and Rafiei, 2011). Seeds were primed for 20 hours, then they were washed with distilled water and air-dried again for 24 hours (Ceritoglu et al., 2024).

After drying process, 30 seeds from each treatment group were selected, positioned between two layers of filter paper. Five milliliters of distilled water were added to each Petri dish at the starting of the study. Germinated seeds were daily controlled for ten days. Germination characteristic including germination percentage, mean germination time, germination index, germination uniformity and germination energy) were determined by the methods of Ceritoglu and Erman (2020). Seeds were classified as germinated when the emerging radicle reached a length of 2 mm. Morphological characteristics such as root length, seedling length, root fresh weight, seedling fresh weight, root dry weight, seedling dry weight and seed vigor index were determined at the end of the experiment.

Data were subjected to analysis of variance to check significant differences ($p < 0.05$ and 0.01) between experimental groups. Grouping of means were calculated by Least Significant Difference (LSD) test.

3. Results

Analysis of variance for the germination parameters showed that seed priming promoted statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$) in all germination characteristics (Table 1). However, priming treatments did not affect morphological traits except for root length that was affected at 5% (Table 2).

The lowest germination percentage (75%) was determined in HA2, while the highest one (97.50%) was observed in GA2. Mean germination time was the lowest (1.037 days) in control seeds, whereas it was the highest (1.975 days) in HA1 treated seeds. The lowest germination index (11.15) was determined in HA2 treated seeds, while the highest one (19.62) was obtained from control seeds. Germination uniformity was the highest (77.15) in control seeds, whereas it had the lowest value (40.53) in HA2 treated seeds. Germination energy was high in control, GA1 and GA 2 treatments, however, it decreased with increasing HA doses (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of seed priming on germination characteristics in lentil

	Germination percentage	Mean germination time (MGT)	Germination index (GI)	Germination uniformity	Germination energy
Control	92.50 bc	1.037 c	19.62 a	77.15 a	77.00 a
HA1	88.75 c	1.45 b	15.70 b	55.65 b	46.00 b
HA2	75.00 d	1.975 a	11.15 c	40.53 c	11.00 c
GA1	95.00 ab	1.113 c	19.05 a	72.40 a	73.00 a
GA2	97.50 a	1.100 c	19.15 a	73.55 a	74.00 a
Mean	89.75	1.394	16.38	61.43	51.75
P-Value (%)	1	1	1	1	1
LSD	10.40 **	0.32**	3.94 **	16.93 **	33.92 **

(** : $p < 0.01$)

The shortest root length (5.20 cm) appeared in the HA2 treatment, whereas the longest root length (6.65 cm) was obtained under the GA1 application. Seedling length, root fresh weight, seedling fresh weight, root dry weight, seedling dry weight and seedling vigor index varied between 4.15-5.05 cm, 0.082-0.034 g, 0.037-0.046 g, 0.071-0.071 g, 0.016-0.024 g and 1.30-6.61, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of seed priming on germination characteristics in lentil

	Seedling length	Root length	Root fresh weight	Seedling fresh weight	Root dry weight	Seedling dry weight	Seedling vigor index (SVI)
Control	4.90	5.75 d	0.028	0.042	0.071	0.016	6.61
HA1	4.15	5.90 c	0.030	0.040	0.017	0.020	1.58
HA2	5.05	5.20 e	0.034	0.037	0.017	0.017	1.30
GA1	4.70	6.65 a	0.030	0.046	0.019	0.024	1.82
GA2	4.60	6.30 b	0.029	0.042	0.018	0.019	1.74
Mean	4.70	5.88	0.031	0.041	0.031	0.019	2.83
P-Value	N.S.	*	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.
LSD	2.43	2.59 *	0.011	0.016	0.097	0.015	9.058

(* : $p < 0.05$, ** : $p < 0.01$, N.S: No significant difference)

When Tables 1 and 2 are evaluated together, it becomes clear that seed priming treatments mainly affected germination-related traits in lentil, whereas seedling biomass formation was less responsive in the short term. In particular, gibberellic acid treatments not only accelerated the germination process but also promoted a more uniform pattern of germination. The concurrent increase in germination percentage, germination index, and germination energy indicates that a large proportion of seeds germinated rapidly and within a narrow time interval. In contrast, the application of humic acid at high concentration negatively influenced the germination process. The reduction in germination percentage, along with lower germination uniformity and germination energy, suggests that germination was both delayed and more uneven among seeds. This response indicates that excessive humic acid may hinder water uptake and delay the activation of metabolic processes required for successful germination.

Evaluation of the morphological traits presented in Table 2 shows that, except for root length, most parameters exhibited limited sensitivity to the applied treatments. This finding suggests that hormone and organic matter applications primarily influence early physiological processes, while biomass accumulation becomes more pronounced at later developmental stages. The increase in root length observed under gibberellic acid treatments indicates that this hormone stimulates early root growth, potentially providing an advantage during early seedling establishment. Overall, these results are consistent with previous studies reporting the stimulatory role of gibberellic acid during germination and the inhibitory effects of high humic acid concentrations on early physiological processes (Finch-Savage and Leubner-Metzger, 2006; Nardi et al., 2002).

4. Discussion

The enhancements detected in the GA-treated seeds align with the known physiological functions of gibberellins, which stimulate the breakdown of stored reserves and promote cellular elongation (Finch-Savage and Leubner-Metzger, 2006). These processes facilitate quicker radicle protrusion and contribute to more synchronized seedling emergence. Conversely, the decline in germination and early seedling performance under elevated humic acid levels is likely linked to an increase in the osmotic potential surrounding the seed, which can impede water absorption and disrupt early metabolic activation (Bewley and Black, 1994). The lack of statistically significant differences in biomass parameters indicates that the physiological improvements induced during the initial germination phase do not immediately translate into measurable biomass gains within the limited duration of the experiment. Overall, GA priming (50 and 100 mg L⁻¹) appears to be a reliable pre-sowing treatment for lentil, whereas humic acid applications require careful dose optimization. Recent studies on chickpea indicate that humic acid can positively influence vegetative growth, root system development, and yield components (Rose et al., 2014). Ulukan et al. (2012), indicated that humic acid applications promoted early plant development under semi-arid environmental conditions, while Kahraman (2017), found meaningful improvements in yield attributes following its application. Similarly, Dönder and Toğay (2021), noted that humic acid improved yield performance of chickpea particularly under dryland conditions, underscoring its potential as a growth- and yield-enhancing agent. Öktem et al. (2013a) evaluated the effects of pre-sowing humic acid applications at 0%, 1.25%, 2.5%, 5%, and 10% on red lentil in Harran Plain in Şanlıurfa during 2010–2011. Their results indicated that 5% of HA produced the highest grain yield. Öktem et al. (2013b) examined the effects of humic acid on wheat seeds at equivalent concentration and noted that 5% and 10% of HA resulted in the greatest grain yield.

Low concentrations enhance membrane permeability, facilitating water and nutrient uptake as well as promoting root development (Çelik and Katkat, 2007). However, high concentrations can increase osmotic pressure around the seed, slowing water absorption and

ultimately reducing germination rate and seedling vigor (Bewley and Black, 1994). Küçük and Çimrin (2020), observed that while low doses of humic acid improved germination and root growth, higher doses inhibited water uptake and early metabolic processes, leading to reduced seedling development. HA2 treatment showed numerically lower biomass values, indicating a non-significant downward trend in the experiment. Karakurt et al. (2009), also reported that excessive humic acid applications can suppress early physiological processes. These findings align with the reduced germination percentage and germination uniformity observed with HA2 in the present study.

The higher germination rate, shorter germination time, and more uniform emergence observed in the control group can be attributed to the hydropriming treatment applied to these seeds. Hydropriming is a preparation technique in which seeds are allowed to absorb water in a controlled manner and are then re-dried, activating metabolic processes without initiating radicle emergence. This treatment enables seeds to take up water more quickly and evenly, promotes earlier enzyme activation, and accelerates the mobilization of stored reserves. It also supports key processes required for successful germination, such as DNA repair, the regulation of respiration, and the activation of stress-mitigating pathways. Numerous studies have demonstrated that hydropriming increases germination speed, shortens mean germination time, and leads to more synchronized seedling emergence. Therefore, the superior performance of the control seeds results from the physiological advantages conferred by hydropriming, without the need for any chemical stimulants. This positive effect becomes even more pronounced when compared with the delaying influence of high humic acid doses.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that seed priming with gibberellic acid and humic acid differentially influences germination behavior and early seedling development in lentil. The results clearly indicate that gibberellic acid applications were more effective than humic acid in improving germination-related traits, particularly germination percentage, germination uniformity, germination energy, and early root elongation. Among the tested treatments, GA₂ (100 mg L⁻¹) provided the most consistent improvement in germination performance, suggesting that this concentration is suitable for promoting rapid and uniform seed emergence. Although gibberellic acid treatments enhanced early physiological processes associated with germination, these improvements did not result in significant increases in seedling biomass parameters within the short experimental period. This finding suggests that the primary role of gibberellic acid is related to the activation and synchronization of early metabolic events rather than immediate biomass accumulation. In contrast, humic acid exhibited a dose-dependent response. While humic substances are known to support plant growth under appropriate conditions, the higher humic acid concentration (4000 mg L⁻¹) negatively affected germination percentage and uniformity. This response indicates that excessive humic acid may interfere with water uptake and delay the initiation of metabolic processes required for successful germination. Therefore, careful adjustment of humic acid dosage is essential to avoid potential inhibitory effects during the early stages of plant development.

The relatively strong performance observed in the control treatment highlights the effectiveness of hydropriming as a simple and low-cost technique to improve germination characteristics. Overall, the findings suggest that gibberellic acid priming within the range of 50–100 mg L⁻¹ can be considered a practical and reliable method for enhancing early establishment in lentil, whereas humic acid applications require cautious dose optimization. Further studies under field conditions are recommended to evaluate whether these early advantages translate into improved growth and yield performance at later developmental stages.

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